

TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract: A foreign language is an academic subject that involves the creation of an artificial language environment for students, which predetermines the variable inclusion of various digital learning tools in new perspectives for teaching a foreign language.

Key words : various software systems, including simulators, test programs, graphic editors, multimedia presentations, graphs, tables, Web-quest (webquest).

Due to the unfavorable situation associated with the new coronavirus infection COVID-2019, students and teachers had to switch to a new type of education - distance learning. Unfortunately, our education system was not quite ready for such a dramatic transition to online learning. The teaching community found itself in a situation where it was necessary to make a digital breakthrough in a month, rethink new forms of education and understand how to transfer group and individual classes online.

This means that the role of educators is changing and should be aimed at helping the development of the younger generation as active members of society. We need to learn new ways to communicate with our students outside of our classrooms, it's time to define what the new learning should look like.

In all the existing and constantly updated variety, it is necessary to create and update in real time a certain typology of digital technologies in teaching a foreign language, determine the possibilities of their use and model the methodology for working with them in the context of a change in the methodological paradigm. In the improvement of the material base, software and methodological support, in the acquisition of relevant experience by teachers, the prospect of successful implementation of the digitalization of education is seen.

During the pandemic, teachers began to master educational platforms that helped both in mastering new knowledge and in testing and assessing students' knowledge. For example, most online platforms have become free during the pandemic.

Modern digital tools for teaching a foreign language help us stimulate and develop cognitive activity in students.

The most common is multimedia activity. MZ is a lesson using digital technologies, various programs and technical means to effectively influence the student.

During this lesson, you can use various software systems, including simulators, test programs, graphic editors, multimedia presentations, graphs, tables. As the practice of introducing such tools into the educational process shows, their use effectively affects the student, who develops the ability to learn about the world around him, the skills to use knowledge and skills in a real life context, creative thinking, making optimal decisions in a difficult situation, research skills, the ability to information processing.

Multimedia presentations are the next available technology to include in the learning process and require a computer and a projector to use them.

Forms of inclusion of presentations in classes depend on their content and its goals. So, the following are considered effective goals of application: the study of new material; fixing a new topic; checking the assimilation of grammatical material, preparing for state exams.

A training video is a type of Internet resource that allows you to view videos and complete tasks for them, which is used both online and offline. Tasks can be included in the video itself, or in special workbooks. Among the most popular resources are the following:

1) family English ESL is an online resource that provides a variety of videos and materials for learning new topics and for reviewing vocabulary and grammar.

2) Khan Academy - An online resource that provides a variety of videos and materials for them for studying and, mainly, repetition of materials in various subjects, preparing for international exams. There is a "Teachers" section on the site, which allows you to add tasks to the video online.

The question of the choice of methods for conducting training sessions is an everyday one, since the topics and specific situations of training are very diverse. Not a little important aspect is the development of various techniques and teaching methods using and applying various technologies, such as:

Web-quest (webquest) - organization of project activities of students using Internet resources. It involves group work of students. The teacher's role is to compile Internet resources so that only one aspect of the topic is revealed by each group. At the second stage of the quest, the groups are re-formed so that each new group has one representative from each primary group. During the passage of the webquest, students must answer one general question that is debatable. An educational webquest is often presented as a site (a group of sites) that contains all the information for students to complete a particular task.

There are two types of webquests:

Short-term, in order to deepen and generalize the knowledge of knowledge and its integration, is carried out in one to three lessons.

Long-term, to deepen and transform students' knowledge, designed for a semester or academic year.

The final result of the work in the quest is the publication of students' work in the form of web pages and sites.

When drafting a quiz, keep the following in mind:

- ✓ there should be a clear description of the roles of participants, i.e. quest script.
- ✓ The main task should be understandable, interesting and feasible for students of this age. It is important to clearly formulate the final result of independent work of students.
- ✓ must be a list of information resources needed to complete the task.
- ✓ there should be a description of the procedure for working at each stage of the quest and the stages of work themselves.
- ✓ guiding questions, for the organization of educational work, aiming students at a certain activity.

Using blogs in teaching AI. If a site regularly posts one person's news, we call it a blog.

For blogging, you can use website builders, or you can use special designers designed for blogging.

Blog .ru (<http://blog.ru/>) is a specialized service for keeping diaries on the Internet. After registering on the server, We enter personal data and we are offered a minimal user interface.

Blogger (www.blogger.com) is Google's blogging app, and it has an intuitive builder interface that's pretty much the same as a website builder, as well as a huge number of free templates. It can be uploaded to media content, the allocated space of 10 GB is shared with Google Drive. You can also use other tools for blogging: social networks, Sway, online boards.

A special place is occupied by an online service, Google-form, it allows you to create a feedback form, online testing and surveys for students.

One of the necessary skills for a teacher is the ability to work with cloud services such as:

- Google Cloud

- Cloud OneDrive
- Cloud Yandex

Using cloud storage in the educational process:

Provides access to documents and learning materials for parents and students, with the protection of lesson plans, statements and other documents that should be "at hand".

Allows you to collaborate with other educators on curricula or collaborative projects, you can send learning materials created at home to the cloud so that you can access them from your work computer or phone.

How can a student use cloud storage?

Post educational materials.

Use them to collaborate on projects.

Submit work to a teacher, providing access via a link or sending work by mail, and so on.

For the effectiveness of our work, we can use online boards.

Online boards are an interactive tool that allows you to place various materials in a single space, provide access to them to a group of people of your choice, jointly view and edit information posted on the board.

An online interactive whiteboard is organized in the form of a large window with scrolling horizontally, vertically or in both directions. The possibilities for posting and editing information are different for different online boards. All boards work with textual information, which is placed on the board in the form of stickers - text fields that imitate leaflets attached to the board.

Conceptboard (conceptboard.com) is an interesting online board where you can draw (like in Paint), post text and audio fragments, stickers and text blocks, images. You can use your Google account to sign in. You can invite other users to collaborate on the whiteboard, you can simply use it in class instead of an interactive whiteboard or a regular one. Its only drawback is that the resource is paid.

RealtimeBoard (realtimeboard.com) has a large number of templates for various purposes, which makes it easier to work with the application. You can use text, stickers, draw with a pencil, and use forms to attach files with images, videos, tables, etc. You can use your Google account to sign in, the free use case allows you to connect up to 3 users to the board, which is suitable for small projects, and the board can also be used simply for explaining material instead of a presentation.

LinoIt (linoit.com) universal board. It provides the ability to work with notes, stickers, graphics, videos from social networks. Unlike the previous examples, there is no drawing, but the resource is absolutely free. After registering, you can grant access to other participants who do not need to register, which is convenient for the teacher. Despite the fact that it does not have a Russian interface, it supports Cyrillic. Accessing the board via a link makes it possible to embed it in your web page.

Programs such as zoom and skype have shown themselves to be the most popular platforms during the pandemic. They allow teachers to conduct lessons online, regardless of the number of students.

The use of digital technologies in the classroom creates unlimited opportunities for the teacher and students. Working with virtual models, video, animation, sound, graphics attract students' attention to the topic. Digital technologies accompany the course of the lesson in accordance with its plan, but cannot take up most of the lesson. They add elements that cannot be implemented in practice: gif images as a means of evaluating online work, video clips to simulate the creation of a language environment in the classroom.

Thus, digital learning technologies have a huge learning potential. It is necessary to test in a real educational context their ability to stimulate various types of speech activity and the ability to organize the contact and non-contact educational process in a new way.

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced educational institutions around the world to suddenly use the full range of available technological tools to create distance learning for pupils and students in all areas. Educators around the world have embraced new opportunities to build their learning differently and with more flexibility, resulting in the potential for education to be accessible to students around the world. These are new ways of learning that were previously largely unused and not in demand.

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